

N-Hydroxy-N, N'-diphenylformamidine as Gravimetric Reagent for Pd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II)

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N-Hydroxy-N, N'-diphenylformamidine has been used as a gravimetric reagent for Pd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II) at pH 2.0, 3.0 and 5.5 respectively. The complexes have 1:2 metal-ligand composition.

N-SUBSTITUTED phenylhydroxylamines have been used as analytical reagents since long. Cupferron¹, N-nitrosophthalhydroxylamine², N-benzoylphenylhydroxylamine³⁻⁶, N-an isoylphenylhydroxylamine⁷, N-phenylazo-phenylhydroxylamine⁸ are noteworthy. Ley⁹ and others^{10,11,12} have shown that imidoylchlorides react with phenylhydroxylamines to form hydroxamic acid derivatives, but their use in inorganic analysis have not been studied, Agarwal¹³ and Kodala and Mishra¹⁴ have studied some imidoyl derivatives of phenylhydroxylamine for their chelating properties. In the present investigation we have studied N-hydroxy-N, N'-diphenyl formamidine and found it to be an excellent reagent for palladium(II), copper (II) and nickel (II).

Experimental

Preparation of the reagent: The reagent, I, was prepared by the condensation of N-phenyl formimidoyl chloride and N-phenylhydroxylamine in ether medium.

Procedure: An ice-cold solution of N-phenylformimidoyl chloride (0.040 mole, 5.6 g) in 80 ml. ether was gradually added to freshly prepared N-phenylhydroxylamine (0.041 mole, 4.5 g) dissolved in 40 ml. ether, keeping the temperature in between 0°-5°, shaking after each addition and adding sodium bicarbonate solution (1%) to neutralize the HCl formed during the reaction. Shaking was continued for another 10 min after complete addition of imidoyl chloride solution. The ethereal layer was separated and ether removed by evaporation. The residue obtained was crystallized from 50% aqueous alcohol in pale yellow needles (5.0 g; 60% yield). Analysis: (Found: C, 70.37; H, 5.52; N, 13.25%. Calc. for C₁₈H₁₂ON₂: C, 70.29; H, 5.66; N, 13.20%). The substance was insoluble in water and soluble in acetone, benzene, ethanol and chloroform.

Reaction towards metal ions: Preliminary studies on the precipitating properties of the reagent with different metal ions were carried out adopting conventional procedures. The results are recorded in Table 1.

Determination of Pd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II): Preparation of solutions: Reagent solution was

TABLE 1—REACTION OF N-HYDROXY-N, N'-DIPHENYLFORMAMIDINE WITH METAL IONS

Ion	pH for initial precipitation	pH for complete precipitation	Colour of ppt.	Properties of the complex
Cu ²⁺	—	2.0-7.0	Red-brown	Granular, stable towards heat
Cd ²⁺	6.2	N.Q.	Pale-yellow	Fine ppt., unstable towards heat
Co ²⁺	4.0	5.0-7.0	Dirty-brown	Granular, slightly soluble in water
Fe ²⁺	2.0	5.0-7.0	Blue-black	Granular, unstable towards heat
Fe ³⁺	2.0	4.5-7.0	Blue-black	Granular, unstable towards heat
Hg ²⁺	4.2	5.4-7.0	Yellow	Fine ppt., unstable towards heat
Mn ²⁺	6.3	N.Q.	Brown	Unstable towards heat
Ni ²⁺	3.8	4.7-7.0	Yellow	Granular, stable towards heat
Pb ²⁺	7.4	N.Q.	Yellow	Fine ppt., unstable towards heat
Pd ²⁺	—	1.5-7.0	Brown	Granular, stable towards heat
Sn ⁴⁺	6.4	N.Q.	Yellow	Fine ppt., unstable towards heat
Ti ⁴⁺	—	2.0-4.0	Orange	Unstable towards heat
Zn ²⁺	6.3	N.Q.	Yellow	Fine ppt., unstable towards heat
VC ₂ ⁺	—	N.Q.	Brown	Unstable towards heat, sol. in alcohol
MoO ₄ ²⁻	—	N.Q.	Orange-red	Unstable towards heat, sol. in alcohol

N. Q.: Not quantitative.

prepared by dissolving N, hydroxy-N, N'-diphenylformamide (1 g) in ethanol (100 ml). Standard solutions of Cu(II) and Ni(II) were prepared from A.R.B.D.H. copper sulphate and nickel ammonium sulphate respectively and of Pd(II) by dissolving palladium chloride in A.R. HCl, diluting the solution and determining its Pd(II) content with dimethylglyoxime. All other metal ion solutions were prepared by dissolving 1 g of their A.R. quality salts in distilled water (100 g).

General procedure for estimation : Metal ion solutions containing 10-25 mg of the metal were diluted to 150 ml and pH adjusted in between 2.0-3.0 in case of Pd(II), 3.0-3.5 in case of Cu(II) and 5.0-5.5 in case of Ni(II) with the help of N-HCl and 10% sodium potassium tartrate solution. Precipitation was carried out at room temperature by adding the reagent solution dropwise with constant stirring until complete. It was digested on a hot plate at 70° for 30 min, filtered hot, and washed with water till the filtrate gave a blue colour with sodium hydroxide (p-aminophenol is formed by the hydrolytic decomposition of the reagent in acidic medium which gives a blue colour with NaOH). The precipitate was dried to a constant weight at 120°. The results were quantitative within ± 0.4% error.

Interference of foreign ions : Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Mn(II), Cd(II), Be(II), Mg(II), Al(III), Cr(III), As(III), Hg(II) and Th(IV) were found not to form any insoluble complex with the reagent at pH below 3.8, hence they created no interference in the estimation of Pd(II) and Cu(II) by the reagent at 2.5 and 3.5 respectively. When Fe(II) and Fe(III) were present as interfering ions, the digestion period of the complex was increased to 60-70 min to ensure complete decomposition of the iron complexes. Ti(IV), vanadate and molybdate ions which formed insoluble complexes with the reagent at low pH were completely masked by adding 0.5 g of NaF or KF before adding the reagent. The interference due to hydrolysis of Ce(IV) was prevented by the addition of ammonium sulphate (1 g) and of Zr(IV) and Sn(IV) by adding 5 ml of NaF (5% solution).

Results and Discussion

Properties of the complexes : The palladium, copper and nickel complexes of the reagent are dirty brown, reddish brown and pale yellow in colour respectively. They are soluble in chloroform and benzene, sparingly soluble in acetone and only slightly soluble in alcohol. They are crystallised out from acetone which melt at 261°, 198° and 210° respectively. They can be dried at 120° without decomposition. Their analysis show following results.

Pd-complex-Found : Pd = 20.12 ; N = 10.62 ; Calc. for (C₁₃H₁₁N₂O)₂ Pd : Pd = 20.16 ; N = 10.59%.

Cu-Complex-Found : Cu = 13.14, N = 11.79 : Calc. for (C₁₃H₁₁N₂O)₂ Cu : Cu = 13.09, N = 11.74%

Ni-Complex-Found : Ni = 12.17, N = 11.72 : Calc. for (C₁₃H₁₁N₂O)₂ Ni : Ni = 12.20, N = 11.65%

The molecular weight of the complexes determined by cryoscopic method (Rast's Camphor method) was in agreement with the empirical formula weight showing their monomeric nature.

Metal ligand composition : Direct conductometric and pH metric titrations have been done to ascertain the cation ligand ratio in their complexes. Different volumes of the prepared M/50 Pd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II) solutions were taken in beakers, and in each beaker varying volumes of the prepared M/50 reagent solution and absolute alcohol were added in such a way that the total volume in each beaker remained 40 ml. The conductance and pH of the solutions in each beaker were then determined. Graphs between the conductance against the volume of the reagent added for a fixed amount of cation and between pH and the volume of the reagent added for a fixed amount of cation indicated 1 : 2 metal ligand ratios for Pd, Cu and Ni complexes.

Stability of the complexes : The stability of the complexes was determined by Bjerrum's pH-titration technique¹⁵. Titration of the ligand (20ml of 0.02M) with and without metal ion (2ml of 0.02M) was carried out against KOH (0.1M). The values of \bar{n} , average number of ligand bound per metal ion were calculated and after making necessary corrections by Bjerrum's method of successive approximations plotted against the corresponding value of -log R. The values of log K obtained for Pd, Cu and Ni complexes are given below.

Complex	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K
Pd-complex	8.42	7.10	15.52
Cu-complex	7.35	6.02	13.37
Ni-complex	6.89	5.70	12.59

The stability order found is Pd > Cu > Ni which is in accordance with Irving William Rule.

Structure of the complexes : The infrared spectra of the ligand and its complexes were recorded. Their characteristic frequencies are given below :

Compound	-OH (attached to N)	-C=N
N-hydroxy-N, N'-diphenylformamide	cm ⁻¹ 3200	cm ⁻¹ 1615
bis (N-hydroxy-N, N'-diphenylformamide) Pd(II)	—	1550
bis (N-hydroxy-N, N'-diphenylformamide) Cu(II)	—	1555
bis (N-hydroxy-N, N' - diphenylformamide) Ni (II)	—	1545

The ligand shows strong absorption band characteristic of a (O-H) stretching. This band in case of free (O-H) appears at about 3600 cm^{-1} . Hydrogen bonding, however, shifts these bands to lower frequencies. This is true because (O-H) group in the reagent molecule is placed in a very close proximity of the polar (C=N) group. The disappearance of this band in the complexes clearly points to the replacement of hydrogen from (O-H) group by the metal. The lowering of the (C=N) frequency leads to the conclusion that the metal is also coordinated to the nitrogen of the (C=N) group.

Chemistry of the complexes indicates that 2 moles of the reagent, N-hydroxy-N, N'-diphenylformamidine react with a Pd, Cu or Ni ion and that 2 hydrogen atoms have been replaced during the reaction. The replacement of hydrogen atom is expected from β -phenylhydroxylamine which after substitution at the N-position leaves a weakly acidic oxime group (=N-OH). Its acidic property is similar to that of a phenolic group. The same grouping is found in the reagents, cupferron, N-benzoylphenylhydroxylamine and N-phenylazophenylhydroxylamine. Their chelates are formed by the replacement of H atoms with the metal ion. The reaction may, therefore, be represented as follows :

and the structure of the complexes as II

Where M = Pd, Cu or Ni

Conclusion

Imidoyl derivatives of N-phenylhydroxylamine examined by Agarwal^{1,2} for the first time for their chelating properties and studied by us in detail, introduce a new series of organic reagents with the following functional grouping :

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